

IoT data security: How safe do generations think it is?

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ABSTRACT

Internet of Things (IoT) devices have grown rapidly in the last decade. IoT made our lives easier and more efficient but also introduced new potential security threats and risks. Additionally, consumers do not always actively use or even know the security features when available. Older adults lack awareness and technology knowledge about security safeguards compared to their younger counterparts. This is in part because of different modes of computer and Internet use, where older adults tend to be isolated home users and younger adults have greater access to online security resources through work or school. In this paper, the authors look at the correlation between how aware people are of their IoT security and privacy awareness when comparing generations who grew up with computers and those who did not. This creates the research question: ‘What is the difference in cyber security and privacy awareness between generations who grew up with computers and those who did not for IoT consumer solutions?’

Keywords

Internet of Things (IoT), Generations, Privacy, Security, Awareness

INTRODUCTION

Cyber-attacks have been on the rise in recent years, and they will only get worse. Check Point Research (2022) has found that global attacks increased by 28% in the third quarter of 2022 compared to the same period in 2021. The average weekly number of attacks per organization worldwide reached over 1,130.

But not only organizations can be the target of cyber-attacks. According to Fearn (2017), It is becoming all too common for cyber criminals to use consumer devices as pawns in wider attacks. Internet of Things (IoT) devices are more vulnerable to cyberattacks than they ever have been before. Data from Kaspersky (2022) showed that

more than 1.5 billion attacks have occurred against IoT devices in the first six months of 2021. Therefore, it is important for consumers to be more aware of the risks surrounding their IoT devices and know what to do in the event of a cyberattack.

The way people use the Internet of Things is very different in both security and usage. A big factor in computer usage is the differences in generations. Each generation has shared experiences, attitudes, values, and even shared problems that contribute to how they use and interact with IoT (Palfrey & Gasser, 2008).

This paper looks at the correlation between how conscious people are of their IoT security and privacy awareness when comparing generations who grew up with computers and those who did not. The rapid growth of cyberattacks on consumer Internet of Things has led to the question of whether there are differences in the cybersecurity of IoT between generations. Therefore, the goal is to identify whether there are significant differences between generational IoT cybersecurity. With this knowledge, it is possible to create the foundation for future research to identify which measures should be taken to make sure all generations have sufficient knowledge of the security and privacy of their IoT devices. To find significant differences in cybersecurity between generations, this study will perform a literature review and survey research.

By conducting this research, there can be an increase in knowledge about the differences in generations and how they deal with their privacy and security. By knowing how the generations differ, this research can also be applicable to other organizations. Moreover, this research lays the groundwork to make consumers more aware of their data privacy and security. Subsequently, consumers can take advantage of this study and act regarding their privacy and security.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The focus of this research is on the differences between generations who grew up with computers and those who did not, regarding their Internet of Things data security and privacy awareness. The scope is narrowed down to two generations who have IoT devices and live in the Netherlands. The two generations were chosen to be able to make clear comparisons, which are further explained in the next chapter.

Privacy, security, and IoT are defined according to relevant models, laws, and theories. These terms are further explained in the next chapter. Moreover, according to Jiang et al., (2016), there are many differences between people who grew up with computers and those who did not, in the way they operate online today.

The problem is that on average, older adults lack awareness and technology knowledge about security safeguards compared to their younger counterparts (Jiang et al., 2016). These characteristics between people who grew up with data and computers, and those who did not, can influence how they think about their data security regarding IoT.

Current literature explains IoT data security and privacy. Other literature explains the generational differences. However, research has fallen short of describing the correlation between these generational differences and how aware these people are of their IoT data privacy and security. This knowledge gap is the basis of this paper.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The central research question of this study is as follows: *‘What is the difference in cyber security and privacy awareness between generations who grew up with computers and those who did not for IoT consumer solutions?’* This research question was formulated by finding a knowledge gap in the existing literature about IoT. Currently, there is a lot of literature about the different threats and risks, what people should do regarding their privacy and security of IoT, and how IoT can be used in different situations. However, there is little to no knowledge about how different generations react and adapt to the new and upcoming IoT technologies. The research question is divided into a few sub-questions to get a better understanding of the research question and be able to draw a better conclusion.

The first sub-question to be answered is as follows: ‘What are the differences in IoT knowledge and awareness between generations who grew up with computers and those who did not?’ Answering this question will give insight into the differences between generations. Based on

these differences it is possible to assume why and how generations differ in their approach to IoT.

The second sub-question describes data awareness: ‘Do consumers of IoT devices know what companies use their data for?’ This gives an interesting view of the consumer’s knowledge about the data that is used or what it can be used for.

The third sub-question to be answered, reads as follows: ‘What is the difference in cyber security awareness between generations who grew up with computers and those who did not?’

The fourth sub-question to be answered is defined as: ‘What is the difference in privacy awareness between generations who grew up with computers and those who did not?’ Answering both these sub-questions will give insight into why and how generations differ regarding their security and privacy of IoT.

Studying these three sub-questions will give enough insights to draw a valid conclusion on the central research question. Furthermore, it will help with trying to close the knowledge gap and make the research generalizable.

FRAMEWORK

In order to describe the relation of the research variables in the research question an existing model is used: the Trust-risk framework created by Mansour Alraja (2022). The trust-risk framework is used to describe the behavioral intention of Internet of Things (IoT)-enabled healthcare applications. Furthermore, it describes the relationship between risk perception and behavioral intention.

The foundation of this study is based on the fact that few studies have no exploration of generational differences. With the rise of IoT, a lot of products are connected via the internet with each other (Badr et al., 2021). These new products imply unprecedented threats and challenges to existing security solutions and techniques. A lot of people are not aware of these issues. Based on the researchers’ experiences, people that did not grow up with the internet tend to have a lack of awareness and knowledge in comparison to people who grew up with the internet. A framework based on the trust-risk framework and research on other papers has been created to explain the correlation between the variables.

Figure 1: Framework

The following hypothesis were formulated from the model and research question:

H1: Generational differences influence risk awareness.

H2: Being more aware of risks (privacy and security) leads to different behavior using IoT products.

Characteristics of IoT

The Internet of Things (IoT) is built on different characteristics. Studying these characteristics and getting to know the impact on the cybersecurity of IoT is necessary. This way the impact of these characteristics will also be generalizable and more applicable to other upcoming techniques. For IoT to work properly the devices must be able to connect. Connectivity between IoT devices is essential for building IoT systems because the different devices need to identify each other and interact with each other. (Y. Li et al., 2022).

IoT devices can identify each other via interconnection, which also involves a few risks. These risks have an impact on the real-time data in the Internet of Things systems. Security solutions should be adapted and implemented to prevent breaches due to low heterogeneity, which means that the different devices and networks should be compatible (Badr et al., 2021).

IoT devices are constantly sending and receiving data between each other, therefore an IoT network should be highly scalable. Scalability also involves a few risks, IoT devices are more exposed to physical and tampering attacks (Y. Li et al., 2022).

Dynamic changes are the fast-changing states of IoT devices and the increase in the number of IoT devices in a network. Dynamic changes accompany the high scalability of the networks because more devices in a network result in more data transactions and different states of the devices. This increases possible data breaches.

The devices in an Internet of Things network have limited resources available to them. This means that the devices have limited calculation,

storage, bandwidth, and power resources available. These limited resources are easily disabled by some conflicting applications. This calls for better security solutions to prevent and reduce threats.

The most important characteristic of IoT is that it must be easy to use. This characteristic is most important to the users, developers, and operators. However, the ease of use should not be at the expense of de security and privacy of the system (Y. Li et al., 2022).

To be able to understand what impact these characteristics have on the cybersecurity of smart homes and use them in further research, it is important to compile a valid and reliable survey. The survey also needs to make clear why the level of security differs between generations. Central to this research is the characteristics that involve the most cybersecurity-related risks.

Privacy

One interest of this study is whether people from different generations are aware of rules regarding what happens to their data. To understand what happens to this information, data privacy needs to be defined.

Privacy laws are different in various countries. This study has been held in the Netherlands, which means that this study the GDPR will be used as the basis of data protection law. The GDPR is a European privacy regulation. It ensures the careful processing of personal data by businesses and organizations. Moreover, they are not allowed to gather and use more data than is necessary (Netherlands Enterprise Agency, RVO, 2022). For this study, privacy in the survey will be defined according to the GDPR. Participants will not have to know the laws but will be questioned if they know about their existence and if they understand them.

Security

The security of IoT devices and networks can be defined by the CIA triad principles. The three principles of the CIA triad are confidentiality, integrity, and availability. These principles can be used to describe the access, authenticity, and accessibility of data or information (Chai, 2022). This method will be used to describe the security of Internet of Things devices and networks in this paper.

Confidentiality

When trying to access your data, you are asked to log in. This is an example of a confidentiality measure. Confidentiality means that you can only access the data or sensitive information if you are authorized.

Integrity

Integrity can be defined as the occurrence when data is corresponding with reality, so the data can be trusted, and the correctness of the data should not be questioned. To ensure that the data is in the correct state, the data should be reliable, original, and kept safe so it cannot be tampered with.

Availability

Availability means that data or information should always be available to an authorized person whenever they require it. To ensure that data is always available, entities will have to make sure that networks, systems, infrastructure, hardware, and software are always up and running during peak times.

Risk Awareness

The meaning of awareness, according to Gafoor (2012), is as follows: “Awareness is the state or ability to perceive, receive or be conscious of events happening. Without understanding what is happening the observer can confirm that something is happening”. Awareness may also refer to “awareness about”. This means that someone has greater knowledge about something (Ioannou et al., 2020). For example, awareness about the privacy and security issues related to IoT. In this paper “risk awareness” is defined as “the knowledge of the technical elements related to information privacy and security, the understanding that the elements exist in the environment and projection of their impacts in the future” (Correia & Compeau, 2017).

Generational differences

Older adults tend to lack awareness and technology knowledge about security safeguards compared to their younger counterparts (Jiang et al., 2016), which answers sub-question one. These characteristics between people who grew up with data and computers, and those who did not, can influence how they think about their data security regarding the Internet of Things.

The main influence on whether someone grew up with or without computers is their age. According to Palfrey & Gasser (2008), the first

generation that grew up with computers was the Millennials. This generation was born between 1977 and 1992 and they are also known as Digital Natives. To make sure the correct groups are questioned during the survey research, it will be assumed that people born starting from 1985 until now have grown up with computers. However, in the Netherlands, where the survey will be held, people under 18 years old are seen as underaged (Ministerie van Justitie en Veiligheid, 2021). This means for this research individuals born between 1985 and 2003 are within the possible sample frame for the people who grew up with computers.

Because the Digital Natives were born between 1977 and 1992 (Palfrey & Gasser, 2008), individuals born before 1977 can be considered people who grew up without computers. However, to make sure the correct groups are questioned during the survey research, it will be assumed that people born before 1970 have grown up without computers. Moreover, according to Perrin & Duggan (2015), adults born before 1950 lack cell phone ownership and internet use compared to the younger generational groups. For this research individuals born before 1950 will be excluded from the research to increase the chance that the surveyed individuals do have IoT technology installed in their homes.

Behavioral intention of IoT

Each individual has different behavior in how they interact with the Internet of Things devices because of different experiences. According to Ajzen (1991), behavioral intention is defined as follows: “Motivational factors that influence a given behavior where the stronger the intention to perform the behavior, the more likely the behavior will be performed.”

In this paper, the motivational factors that affect behavioral intention when using IoT products are privacy and security awareness.

METHODOLOGY

To gain a clear understanding of the study subject and the knowledge gap, qualitative research (literature research), and quantitative data (survey research) have been collected. The research is collected based on a deductive approach. This means that the researchers first hypothesize the relationships between the variables based on theories, and thereafter collecting data.

Literature research

The literature used in this research is academic literature that has been peer-reviewed, published in well-known journals, and relevant to this research. The literature is used to better understand the various technical definitions linked to the Internet of Things. It is used for the following: (1) Interpreting the general differences in generations about computer use. (2) Explaining cyber security risks related to the use of IoT devices. (2) Explaining privacy risks related to the use of IoT devices. (4) Clarify the definition: of “awareness”. (5) Construing the characteristics of IoT systems.

Survey research

The survey was conducted to find answers to the research (sub)questions and to test the hypotheses. The survey, in the form of a questionnaire, leads to a cost- and time-effective way of collecting data. A survey is also a good way to ensure objectivity and exclude interpretation errors (Nazari et al., 2006).

The unit of analysis is consumers. The sample population for this research is people born between 1950 and 2003 who have IoT devices at home. The sample design is convenience sampling because of the large population and the lack of time (Stratton, S., 2021). Convenience sampling is a type of non-probability sampling that involves the sample being drawn from that part of the population that is close to hand. Convenience sampling is quick and easy to use but has a higher risk of errors, like a coverage error (Stratton, S., 2021). The survey was tested by two random respondents before it was distributed. This is to ensure validity, to check if the survey had the desired effect, and to check whether the survey was understandable.

The survey starts with a short introduction about the research goal and introduces the researchers. The survey covers four different topics based on the central research question:

“What is the difference in cyber security and privacy awareness between generations who grew up with computers and those who did not for IoT consumer solutions.”

The first one is “General”, in this topic a couple of personal questions regarding age and computer knowledge are asked, to separate two different generations: people who grew up using the computer and people who didn’t grow up using the computer. The second topic is about IoT use in general. This topic is about collecting data about the different kinds of IoT devices, the frequency of IoT use, and the basic knowledge of Internet of Things by the participants. The third and fourth

topic collects data of respectively the awareness of cyber security and the awareness of digital privacy. The survey was distributed via personal networks such as WhatsApp and other interpersonal communication.

Measure

The purpose of the survey is to look for a correlation between the variables mentioned in the conceptual model. The questions, measurements, and sources are summed up in table I. The questions including the answers are available in Appendix I.

The final data of the survey was collected using google forms and then exported to SPSS to conduct an in-depth analysis. To measure the correlation between the two variables, Cronbach’s Alphas are calculated.

RESULTS

A total of 33 survey responses were received. However, four respondents were not in our target audience, these answers were not considered in our results. Twelve of the respondents are in the group 1950-1970 and seventeen are in the group of 1985-2003. The mean of people indicating growing up with computers in the first group is 2.42 and in the second group a mean of 4.06. This shows that there are generational differences between the two research groups.

The results of the survey are analyzed using SPSS. Firstly, the internal reliability is calculated from the survey using Cronbach’s Alpha (Cohen, 1988). The formula to calculate the Cronbach alpha is as follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{N \cdot \bar{c}}{\bar{v} + (N - 1) \cdot \bar{c}}$$

Figure 2: Cronbach’s Alpha

N= number of items, \bar{c} = average covariance between item pairs, \bar{v} = average variance.

A level above 0.700 is considered acceptable for a variable to be of use. In order to define two groups of different generalizations three questions were focused on this. Calculating a Cronbach alpha resulted in internal reliability of 0.769 for the generalization differences. This means that the internal consistency of this test is high, which leads to the high reliability of the measures.

Furthermore, the analysis of security awareness and privacy awareness measured by four questions both resulted in a Cronbach alpha of 0.779 and 0.885.

To check whether there is a relationship between security awareness and the use of IoT products with the moderating variable age, linear regression is applied.

Table 1 (see Appendix III) shows that the two variables have no significant impact on the dependent variable (0.395 & 0.126). The same is done for privacy awareness and the use of IoT products with the moderating variable age. (see Appendix III)

The variable privacy awareness has a significant impact (<0.05) on the dependent variable (0.006). Generational differences, however, have no significant impact (0.690).

DISCUSSION

The conduction of the study is to find out if there are differences between generations and behavior toward Internet of Things devices. The study focuses on two different generations: those who grew up with a computer and those who did not. The study focuses on the differences in behavior toward their privacy and security awareness.

The survey results show that one variable has a significant impact on the behavior of IoT products. A variable has a significant impact if the value is lower than 0.05. The value of awareness of privacy risks is lower than 0.05 ($0.006 < 0.05$), thus this variable is the only variable that has a significant impact on the behavior of IoT products. Therefore, the correlation of this variable is also high (0.606). This answers sub-question four.

The variables age (growing up with (1985-2003) or without computers (1950-1970)) and security awareness don't have a significant impact. This answers sub-question three. The reason for this could be that consumers know what security means, but they might not know what kind of impact it could have on their data. When they are not aware of the risks they won't act accordingly, which will not impact their behavior toward IoT products. The reason that age makes no difference could be because elderly people have a safer approach to new technologies. Therefore, they might read into the new technologies' risks. As opposed to the new generations, they grow up with new technologies, learn about them in school, and are more likely to be interested in them. Therefore, the knowledge about privacy, security, and awareness doesn't differ anymore.

Furthermore, another non-researched variable that might be of influence is the interest in new technologies. According to Jiang et al., (2016), if someone isn't motivated to learn how to use computers they won't adopt new technologies. Alternatively, if someone is more interested in

these technologies, like IoT, they will most likely widen their knowledge. As a result, they will become more aware of the potential risks and will also act differently. Examining this variable can provide insight into the differences between those who are interested in new technologies and those who are not.

Another variable that might have an influence on the outcome of this research is the education of the consumers. Some who study an IT-related education are likely to learn about new technologies/IoT. So, this might have an impact on their privacy and security awareness and thus will affect the results of future research. This will change the correlation and significant impact. This is in line with Perrin & Duggan (2015), this study shows that people with a college degree or higher are more likely to use the internet.

To add to that, the low correlation and significant impact can also be explained due to the fact that the authors didn't research what time people spend on their phones/laptops/being online. According to Albert et al., (2019), younger generations who spend more time on social media are more likely to be exposed to online interactions and IoT devices. Therefore, they are more likely to come across more articles, newspapers, or terms of services on websites. Which will probably help improve their knowledge about privacy and security awareness.

When analyzing the survey results, an interesting pattern regarding the knowledge of consumers about their data appears. More than 95% of the respondents admitted that they do not read the terms of agreements when installing their IoT devices. Moreover, more than 60% of the respondents do not know about the data protection laws such as the GDPR and more than 73% do not understand these laws, which answers sub-question two. This is in line with a study performed by Deloitte (2017), where more than 90% of consumers admitted to not reading and understanding the terms of services from companies. Because IoT devices can collect and store big amounts of sensitive data (Badr et al, 2021), this could be a risk for consumers in the coming years. Future (qualitative) research could indicate why consumers do not read or understand the terms of services from IoT providers and how to make them more aware of the risks of not doing so.

CONCLUSION

This research has provided an answer to the following research question: “What is the difference in cyber security and privacy awareness between generations who grew up with computers and those who did not for IoT consumer solutions”. This research states that age and security awareness do not have a significant impact on each other. Age is considered as people born between 1950 - 1970 and 1985 - 2003.

This research is built on two hypotheses, namely: (H1) Generational differences influence risk awareness and (H2) Being more aware of risks (privacy and security) leads to the different behavior of Internet of Things products.

According to the results, hypothesis one can be rejected, because the results show that age doesn't have a significant impact. The team can slightly accept hypothesis two. The results show that the awareness of privacy has a significant impact on the behavior toward IoT products and the awareness of security doesn't. To be able to reject and accept hypotheses on more reliable and valid data, further research can be improved by the number of respondents. The number of respondents in this survey was only 33. Having a higher response rate will enhance the results of the survey. Hence, the survey can be improved by increasing the sample size and the processing time of the survey. This will result in a higher response, which will lead to more accurate data.

Limitations

The first and most important potential limitation is time. This research has been conducted in a small time frame, therefore convenience sampling was used. The sample size consists of 33 people, with a small majority being students. Therefore the sample size is not entirely representative. Stratified sampling would have been an alternative, because of the two homogeneous groups. The survey link was shared with the personal network of the researchers, which contains a lot of students. Therefore, the sample frame is not completely representative. Also, because of the time, there was a small number of respondents to the survey (33). Because of this small number, the researchers were unable to clean the data for abnormalities. There was also a limitation in the survey method. To conduct a good analysis of the results there should have been more “Likert scale answers” in the survey instead of closed questions. This would have resulted in a more accurate analysis of the data and could have led to a more complete collection of insights.

To increase the chance of acceptance of the hypothesis, an additional survey could have been

conducted to ask the respondents more specific questions about privacy and security, in order to test their knowledge about it further. As a result, the internal validity of the research could be increased.

Further research

The survey has only been shared with Dutch citizens; therefore, it might be interesting to research how the difference will be in other countries, or globally.

It would also be interesting to study why users of IoT do not read or maybe do not understand the terms and conditions given by the IoT providers. Based on this, IoT companies or government entities can develop a strategy to enable IoT users to read and understand the terms and conditions better.

Finally, Future (qualitative) research could indicate why consumers do not read or understand the terms of services from IoT providers and how to make them more aware of the risks of not doing so.

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APPENDIX I SURVEY QUESTIONS

In what year were you born?

- – 1949
- 1950 – 1970
- 1971 – 1984
- 1985 – 2003
- 2004 +

I grew up using computer devices

Likert scale: 1 Strongly disagree – 5 strongly agree

My computer knowledge is above average.

Likert scale: 1 Strongly disagree – 5 strongly agree

I know what Internet of Things devices are.

Likert scale: 1 Strongly disagree – 5 strongly agree

How many IoT devices do you have?

- None
- 1 or 2
- 3 – 5
- 6 or more
- I really don't know exactly

Which kind of IoT devices do you have?

- Home security
- Activity trackers
- Smart sound
- Climate system
- Other...

For what purpose did you buy your IoT device(s)?

- Security (Camera, doorbell, alarm system)
- Entertainment (Bose/Sonos Sound system)
- Comfort / ease (Weather station, smart fridge)
- Information gathering (Google home, Alexa)
- Other...

Have you installed the IoT devices yourself?

- No
- Yes, but with someone's help
- Yes, all by myself

Are you aware that IoT devices are always connected to the internet?

- No
- Yes

Does a certain brand (reputation) influence your choice? (e.g. Google, Amazon)

- No
- Yes

I completely understand what digital security means.

Likert scale: 1 Strongly disagree – 5 strongly agree

Digital security is very important to me.

Likert scale: 1 Strongly disagree – 5 strongly agree

I am aware of the security risks of my IoT device(s).

Likert scale: 1 Strongly disagree – 5 strongly agree

My awareness of security risks influences the way I use my IoT device(s).

Likert scale: 1 Strongly disagree – 5 strongly agree

About which IoT security risks are you aware of?

- I am not aware of any IoT security risks
- Data breaches
- Physical attacks
- Tampering attacks
- The authentication of devices
- Other...

Do you use multiple different passwords for your devices?

- No
- Yes
- I don't know

Do you update your IoT devices regularly?

- No
- Yes
- I don't know

Do you update your router/modem regularly?

- No
- Yes
- I don't know

Do you regularly check for updates?

- Yes
- No

How do you secure your devices?

- Password
- Fingerprint
- Back-up email
- Two-step authentication
- Face recognition
- I don't know

I completely understand what digital Privacy means.

Likert scale: 1 Strongly disagree – 5 strongly agree

Digital privacy is very important to me.

Likert scale: 1 Strongly disagree – 5 strongly agree

I am aware of the privacy risks of my IoT device(s).

Likert scale: 1 Strongly disagree – 5 strongly agree

This awareness has influenced the way I use my IoT device(s).
Likert scale: 1 Strongly disagree – 5 strongly agree

Do you trust companies with your data?

- No
- Yes

Do you read the terms of agreement when installing the IoT Device?

- No
- Yes

Do you understand these policies?

- No
- Yes

Do you know about the data protection laws?

- No
- Yes

Do you understand the data protection laws?

- No
- Yes

Do you know what companies can do with your data?

- No
- Yes

Do you want to mention anything else that has not yet been mentioned or asked and is relevant for this study

APPENDIX II SURVEY QUESTIONS

Construct name	Measurement	Source
General	<p>Close ended question In what year were you born? <i>The first generation that grew up with computers were the Millennials born between 1977 and 1992 (Palfrey & Gasser, 2008).</i></p> <p>Five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neutral, 4=agree, 5=strongly agree) I grew up using computer devices. My computer knowledge is above average.</p>	<p>(Palfrey & Gasser, 2008)</p> <p>Own development</p>
IoT General	<p>Five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neutral, 4=agree, 5=strongly agree) I know what Internet of Things devices are.</p> <p>Close ended question How many IoT devices do you have? Which kind of IoT devices do you have? For what purpose did you buy your IoT device(s)? Have you installed the IoT devices yourself? Are you aware that IoT devices are always connected to the internet? Does a certain brand (reputation) influence your choice? (e.g., Google, Amazon)</p>	Own development
Security risks	<p>Five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neutral, 4=agree, 5=strongly agree) I completely understand what digital security means. Digital security is very important to me. I am aware of the security risks of my IoT device(s). My awareness of security risks influences the way I use my IoT device(s).</p> <p>Close ended question About which IoT security risks are you aware of? <i>Classification of Security Risks in the Iot Environment</i> Do you use multiple different passwords for your devices? Do you update your IoT devices regularly? Do you update your router/modem regularly? Do you regularly check for updates? How do you secure your devices?</p>	<p>Own development</p> <p>(Cvitić, Vujić, & Husnjak 2016)</p>
Privacy risks	<p>Five-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neutral, 4=agree, 5=strongly agree) I completely understand what digital Privacy means. Digital privacy is very important to me. I am aware of the privacy risks of my IoT device(s). This awareness has influenced the way I use my IoT device(s).</p> <p>Close ended questions Do you trust companies with your data? Do you read the terms of agreement when installing the IoT Device? Do you understand these policies? Do you know about the data protection laws? Do you understand the data protection laws? Do you think you understand what companies do with your data?</p> <p>Open ended question Do you want to mention anything else that has not yet been mentioned or asked and is relevant for this study?</p>	Own development

APPENDIX III COEFFICIENTS TABLE

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1,328	,843		1,576	,131
	I grew up using computer devices.	,165	,190	,186	,870	,395
	I am aware of the security risks of my IoT device(s).	,359	,225	,340	1,596	,126

a. Dependent Variable: My awareness of security risks influences the way I use my IoT device(s).

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,679	,707		,961	,348
	I grew up using computer devices.	,066	,162	,078	,405	,690
	I am aware of the privacy risks of my IoT device(s).	,606	,196	,592	3,086	,006

a. Dependent Variable: My awareness of privacy risks influences the way I use my IoT device(s).